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DECIDE FOR NEAR-REAL-TIME USE OF OCEAN COLOUR DATA IN MANAGEMENT OF TOXIC ALGAE BLOOMS

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Requirements Document

in co-operation with

**Centre for Coastal and Marine Sciences-
Plymouth Marine Laboratory
Plymouth, UK**

**Institute of Marine Research
Bergen, Norway**

EUROPEAN SPACE AGENCY CONTRACT REPORT

The work describes in this report was done under ESA contract. Responsibility for the contents resides in the author or organisation that prepared it.

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REMARK This report is the project deliverable focusing on the requirement for information within the HAB monitoring in Norwegian waters. The report is merged with the document for analysis of the service needs, and published under a joint NERSC report no. 180.	
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ESA STUDY CONTRACT REPORT			
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<p>ABSTRACT:</p> <p>The importance of the aquaculture industry is significant for the Norwegian economy and the employment in coastal parts of Norway. The development of the industry over the last decades, placed Norway as the world largest export nation for aquaculture fish species, exporting in 1998 around 390,000 tonnes of farmed salmon and trout.</p> <p>The aquaculture industry has many challenges in order to maintain a profitable business. Among the challenges are the treats from potentially harmful natural algae blooms in the water surrounding the aquaculture sites. However, in order to implement efficient mitigation actions an early warning of the harmful algae bloom events are essential.</p> <p>The main objective of this study is to identify, demonstrate and validate the use of satellite Earth observation information in support of the existing command chain for disaster management operations in relation to monitoring of harmful algae bloom (HAB) in Norwegian waters. This ALGEINFO service has been established in support of the awareness of the public and the aquaculture industry on the occurrence of HAB events. The project specifically addresses the development and implementation of a pre-operational demonstration towards a sustainable service for harmful algae bloom monitoring and management decision support, related to the effective management of aquaculture and partly fisheries, public health, and ecosystem problems and mainly harmful algae blooms.</p> <p>The current monitoring and decision making system for harmful algae bloom situation in Norwegian waters are strongly pending on early warning and efficient monitoring and predictions of eventually harmful bloom events. This can only be achieved through an efficient observational system based on an integrated approach using multiple information sources, including the current network of 27 stations for <i>in situ</i> observations, dedicated ship observations, satellite Earth observation data, and numerical predictions models for simulations of the bloom evolution.</p> <p>The capability of remote sensing based information products (mainly pigment concentration, turbidity and sea surface temperature) in combination with other observations has proven to be valuable for the early detection and monitoring of the development and decay of algae bloom events. However, the limitations of EO data observations with respect to among other cloud cover, algae specie discrimination, and subsurface observation capability encourage an integrated implementation strategy where the optimal information are obtained from the various sources available.</p> <p>It is concluded that the awareness of some of the potential information on algae blooms based on EO data sources are present within the current Norwegian monitoring service ALGEINFO, as well as the contingency plan for HAB situations in Norwegian waters. A further demonstration, evaluation and implementation through actual demonstration of EO data from ocean colour sensors is required in order to fully explore and define the role and use of EO data in support of the current activities.</p> <p>This report specifically adressess the description of current system for monitoring of HAB events in Norwegian waters and the specific requirements for information set forward among the parties involved in sampling, analysing and providing information on actual HAB events.</p> <p>The work described in this report was done under ESA contract. Responsibility for the contents resides in the authors or organisation that prepared it.</p>			
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1. Development of the aquaculture industry in Norway

The Norwegian aquaculture industry has expanded significantly in recent years, as reflected by increases of well over 100-fold in the annual production of salmon in the last decade. (Figure 1). This reflects not only the growing interest and investment in the Norwegian fish farming industry, but also the increasing efficiency in fish farming methods. The contribution of farmed fish (mostly salmon) exceeded 390,000 tonnes in 1998 and represents about one-third of the total fish export from Norway (Figure 2).

Figure 1. The development in the production of Norwegian salmon in the last decade. (Modified from Norwegian Seafood Export Council).

Figure 2. The Norwegian national income from exports of wild and farmed (mostly salmon) fish in the last decade. (Modified from Norwegian Seafood Export Council).

The commercial interest in fish farming of other species has also increased greatly over recent years. Trout production has recorded a strong increase over the last five years: in 1998 it increased by 44% to 47,500 tonnes. Further, there is a strong belief that halibut will be the next success story

of the aquaculture industry. In 1998, Norway produced 350 000 halibut fry and 250 tonnes of consumable halibut. We are also witnessing a growing interest in the aquaculture of cod and the spotted wolf-fish, and significant research efforts are dedicated to the development of these and other species. Most of the aquaculture production sites are based on various types of floating constructions, where the fish is in direct contact with the surrounding water masses. It may also be noted that the Norwegian shellfish industry is growing rapidly. Great effort has been put into the development of farming of king scallops, and in 1998 two to three billion scallop spats were put into intermediate culture. Further, there is great optimism in Norway's mussel industry; the current prognosis is a 400 % increase in production in the course of 1999. Last year, 605 tonnes of mussels were produced. All told, Norway is now the largest exporter of wild and farmed fish in the world (Figure 3) before China, USA and Denmark. In terms of the Norwegian national economy, fisheries and aquaculture are important contributors. Fish products accounted for over 9 % of the gross national income in 1998. Only the oil and gas sector exceeds this level in the Norwegian economy. Farmed fish represented over one-third of that (Figure 4) or roughly 10 billion NOK. These figures are expected to rise as the existing aquaculture industries grow and diversify in Norway.

Figure 3. Norway is the largest fisheries export nation in the world. Data from 1997. (Modified from Norwegian Seafood Export Council).

Since the coastal fisheries have decreased in the various parts of Norway, the importance of the aquaculture industry has become more significant for the regional employment in some of the most remote coastal parts of the country.

The expected reductions of the off-shore oil and gas exploration activities during the coming decades will lead to an even higher focus on the role of the marine food resources from the fisheries and the aquaculture activities in the Norwegian coastal zone.

Figure 4. Norwegian export products in 1998. (Modified from Norwegian Seafood Export Council).

Because of the importance of fisheries and aquaculture for Norway, the threat of harmful algae blooms (HABs) for the destruction of fish stocks or reduction in the marketability of seafood products is a major concern, both to the fishery management authorities and the industry itself. For example, in 1981 a large HAB caused significant mortality of farmed salmon and economical losses to fish farmers (e.g. Dahl and Tangen, 1993). New HABs in the 1980s and 1990s, and particularly the bloom of *Chrysochromulina polylepsis* in 1988 (Berge *et al.*, 1989, Dundas *et al.*, 1989, Dahl, 1989), have intensified concerns. During this HAB event fish with a market value of 10 million Euros was lost, however caged fish worth of 150 million Euros was towed away from the affected areas probably reducing the losses significantly. For the first time satellite EO data (NOAA AVHRR SST) was used operationally in Norway to monitor the bloom growth, advection and decay (Johannessen *et al.*, 1989).

More recently, in 1998, a large HAB caused mass mortality of fish in farms in the Farsund and Flekkefjord area. Over 360 tonnes of mature salmon died corresponding roughly to 0.1 % of the national export of salmon in 1998 or in the order to 10 million NOK in export value, due to one regional HAB incident! We should note that such events also are compounded by the additional social and economic hardships endured by fish farmers and fish-farming dependent industries. Due to the nature of the aquaculture industry the sites are often located in parts of the Norway where other employment opportunities are limited and that the major parts of the local society often are pending on a few core business activities.

2. Impact of algae blooms on fish farming, marine culture and Human health

2.1 What is an algae bloom?

An algae bloom can be defined as a rapid and marked increase in the local population of phytoplankton. The phenomenon can occur in a matter of days, and can disappear just as rapidly, and may be geographically limited or extend huge areas. Blooms generally mark a convergence of factors that encourage phytoplankton growth. The main factors that cause blooms to occur are natural presence of or introduction of (e.g. through ballast waters from a vessel) an algae specie, sunlight, nutrients, and changes in water temperature. Ocean currents can influence the nutrient supply of blooms, e.g., through up-welling, and they also conspire to maintain or restrain blooms due to the advection (movement) of water both at and below the ocean surface. Physical oceanographic features influence the accumulation of plankton cells and their conditions for growth. Various species has different optimal growth conditions, e.g., related to the water salinity, factors, which may prevent some bloom developments into brackish fjords.

Other physical mechanisms also may be involved in the initiation of bloom conditions. Movement of the water mass onshore and along-shore depends on the currents and wind patterns. All factors that determine the intensity of a bloom are still unclear. The intensity and duration of a bloom is dependent largely on the longevity and stability of the physical oceanographic environment. Mechanisms that contribute to the termination of a bloom include wind-induced vertical mixing of the water column; wind-induced horizontal movement of cells into habitats that are unfavourable for growth (Tester *et al.*, 1991), or a decrease in salinity due to freshwater input (Aldrich and Wilson 1960) as well as the triggering factors mentioned above - lack of nutrients, reduction in solar radiation and water temperature to a certain extent.

2.2 What is a harmful algae bloom?

The last two decades have been marked by an extraordinary expansion in the occurrence and extent of the marine phenomenon called “Harmful algal blooms”, with HAB as the official acronym. HAB are “blooms” of microscopic and macroscopic algae that cause harm in a multitude of ways. Some toxic phytoplankton species are consumed by filter-feeding organisms as food, leading to four different kinds of illness in human consumers: paralytic, neurotoxic, diarrhetic, and amnesic shellfish poisoning (Aune *et al.*, 1995), or PSP, NSP, DSP, and ASP (Figure 5).

HAB may also be associated to massive mortality of fish, both farmed and wild, leading to financial losses to the aquaculture industry. However such bloom may not have any harmful consequences on human beings, directly or through fish consumption.

If for non-toxic algae species, biomass is the criterion most often used to establish bloom status, the potential harmful effects are generally used as far as toxic bloom is concerned. Several of the toxic algae effecting the shellfish are indeed present in very small concentrations compared to most of the algae species affecting the fishes.

We notice that under EC Directive 91/492, European governments are obliged to monitor algae blooms in coastal waters, due to the possible threat to public health posed by toxic algae in shellfish production areas.

Figure 5. Place of harmful algae bloom on the food web, and potential impact on human health.

2.3 Harmful algae blooms in Norway¹

In this century, up to the 1970's, single episodes of mussel toxicity and mortality of wild biota were recorded along the Norwegian coast, but these episodes did not immediately lead to a managing policy. Thereafter, through the 1970's several fish farms were established along the coast. In 1981 a large harmful algae bloom (HAB) of the dinoflagellate *Gyrodinium aureolum* caused significant mortality of farmed salmon and economic losses to fish farmers (e.g. Dahl and Tangen, 1993). The bloom created much public awareness and both the fish farming industry and the authorities acknowledged that harmful algae could be a threat to activities in Norwegian coastal waters. New blooms of *Gyrodinium* followed, and during the 1980's also other phytoplankton species bloomed and caused problems; *Dinophysis* spp. in 1984 (Dahl and Yndestad, 1985), *Chrysochromulina polylepis* in 1988 (Berge *et al.*, 1989; Dundas *et al.*, 1989; Johannessen *et al.*, 1989), recurrent blooms of *Prymnesium* since 1989 (Johnsen and Lein, 1989), *Chrysochromulina leadbeateri* in 1991 (Edvardsen, 1993) and *Chattonella* in 1998 (Horstmann *et al.*, 1998; Durand *et al.*, 1999b). Of about 4,000 marine phytoplankton species, less than 300 are potentially harmful and less than 80 are toxic (Sournia, 1995). However, these belong to several different algal groups (Tables 1 and 2) and consequently are notably different in terms of toxicity or damage characteristics, ecological requirements and bloom dynamics.

¹ An important source of information for this section is Dahl, E. and K. Tangen (1999), The life with harmful algae in Norway – management, ICES 1999 Annual Science Conference, CM 1999/N: 05.

At the beginning of May 1998, a large harmful algae bloom dominated by the flagellate *Chattonella* aff. *verruculosa*, probably in combination with a small amount of *Heterosigma akashiwo*, caused mass mortality of fish in farms in the Farsund and Flekkefjord area. Around 350 tonnes of salmon died, mainly mature fish. This was the first time *Chattonella* was registered in Europe, and also the first time it had appeared in high concentrations which resulted in the death of fish. The algae was later observed at the western coast of Sweden, and affected the whole area of Skagerrak by the beginning of May. Later high concentrations were reported along the west and northern coast of Jutland, resulting in the death of garfish, herring and sand eel. The high concentrations of *Chattonella* in the Skagerrak and along the western coast of Jutland were found in water, which contained unusually high concentrations of nutrients during this time of the year. Large amounts of anthropogenic nitrate from the southern part of the North Sea probably stimulated the extreme growth of the algae bloom together with favourable sun conditions. The bloom had its maximum extension during mid-May and culminated towards the last week of the month. The mussel poisoning incidents by the algae *Alexandrium* and *Dinophysis* were also relatively numerous in the Skagerrak in 1998. The incidence of *D. acuta* and *D. acuminata* remained high during the autumn and the mussels remained toxic until the end of the year.

It is complex to translate the effects of this harmful *Chattonella* bloom in terms of direct financial losses. For mature salmon, losses of about 360 tonnes may be roughly 0.1 % of the national export of salmon in 1998, which translates to a loss of roughly 10 million NOK! The additional export losses due to death of wild fish are not included in this estimate. However the wild fishes have their capability to escape from the HAB areas and the death rate may hence not easily estimated. Further, we should note that true adversity of the bloom is compounded by the additional social and economic hardships endured by fish farmers and fish-farming dependent small and large industries, which in the longer term, may suffer job losses and reduced profits due to mass mortality of farmed and wild fish. The indirect effects of the market attitudes with respect to consumption of fish from a HAB region/country could be very significant, however these are not currently been quantified. It may be reasonable to estimate that the net impact of this one HAB on the Norwegian State may be on the scale of some tens of millions of NOK.

The mitigating actions possible for the aquaculture industry during an HAB situation are limited and dependent upon the nature and extent of the bloom as well as the aquaculture facility and types of farmed fish threatened. The fish may be slaughtered prematurely for use on the market, however in order to set the best quality of the fish, slaughter should be performed after 3 to 12 fast-days (according to specific national regulations) in order to empty fish stomach out and to reduce fat content. An early warning will hence be of significant importance for limitation of losses. Further, enclosure pens with farmed fish may be physically towed to non-threatened waters, if the HAB threat is localised and its distribution well forecasted. All mitigating actions are time consuming. Most importantly, it is vital to warn the aquaculture facilities about the threat of an HAB as early as possible!

Table 1. Prymnesiophytes, diatoms, silicoflagellates, and raphidophytes involved in major harmful phytoplankton blooms in north-western Europe in 1993. ITOX (Ichthyotoxic), MUC (inducing mucus production in gills), ASP (Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning caused by domoic acid). (reproduced from Johnsen et al., 1997, In Kahru and Brown (eds.) Monitoring Algal Blooms; New techniques for detecting large-scale environmental changes).

Species	Period	Affected area
PRYMNESIOPHYTES ^aAcyloxyfucoxanthins and Chl <i>c</i>₃ group (brown sea)		
<i>Chrysochromulina polylepis</i> (ITOX)	April-July	Skagerrak, W and Mid-Norway, Oster/Sørfj.
<i>C. leadbeateri</i> (ITOX)	April-July	Skagerrak and Vestfjord (N Norway)
<i>C. spp.</i> (ITOX?)	March-July	W Norway
<i>Phaeocystis cf. pouchetii</i> (MUC)	Spring	N Norway
<i>P. cf. globosa</i> (MUC)	April-May	Coastal areas of the Netherlands
<i>Prymnesium parvum</i> (ITOX)	July-August	Hylsfjord in Ryfylke (S Norway)
<i>P. patelliferum</i> (ITOX)	July-August	Hylsfjord in Ryfylke (S Norway)
<i>Emiliania huxleyi</i> (non-toxic)	April-Sept.	Along Norwegian coast - offshore
DIATOMS ^bFucoxanthin and Chl <i>c</i>₁₊₂ group (brown sea)		
<i>Chaetoceros convolutus</i> (MUC)	March-April	Rogaland-Helgeland (S to N Norway)
<i>C. spp.</i> (MUC)	March-April	Coastal areas of NW Europe
<i>Pseudonitzschia pseudodelicatissima</i> (ASP)	April-June	SW and Mid-Norway
	August-Sept.	SW and Mid-Norway
<i>Rhizosolenia spp.</i> (MUC)	March-April	Skagerrak
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i> (MUC?)	March-May	Skagerrak
SILICOFLAGELLATES ^cFucoxanthin and Chl <i>c</i>₂ group (yellow-brown sea)		
<i>Dictyocha speculum</i> (ITOX)	Fall	Mid- to N Norway
RAPHIDOPHYTES ^dFucoxanthin, Violaxanthin, and Chl <i>c</i>₁₊₂ group (brown sea)		
<i>Heterosigma akashiwo</i> (ITOX)	April-May	Osterfjord/Sørfjord (Bergen area)
CYANOBACTERIA ^ezeaxanthin, biliprotein group (green-yellow sea)		
<i>Nodularia spumigena</i> (toxic)	July-Sept.	S Skagerrak

^a Johnsen and Sakshaug¹⁵, G. Johnsen, unpublished data, ^{b-c, e} Rowan¹⁰, Johnsen et al.¹⁶, ^d G. Johnsen, unpublished data.

Table 2. Different pigment groups of dinoflagellates involved in major harmful phytoplankton blooms in north-west Europe in 1993. PSP (Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning), DSP (Diarrhetic Shellfish Poisoning), VSP (Venerupin), ITOX (Ichthyotoxic), NH₄ (high ammonium production and O₂ consumption). (Reproduced from Johnsen *et al.*, 1997, In Kahru and Brown (eds.) Monitoring Algal Blooms; New techniques for detecting large-scale environmental changes).

Species	Period	Affected area
DINOFLAGELLATES ^aPeridinin and Chl <i>c</i>₂ group (red-brown sea)		
<i>Alexandrium excavatum</i> (PSP)	Whole year	Mid-Norway (63°N)
<i>Ceratium furca</i> (non-toxic)	Fall	W Sweden (57°N) to Mid-Norway
<i>C. lineatum</i> (non-toxic)	Fall	Norwegian Skagerrak coast
<i>Dinophysis acuminata</i> (DSP)	Fall-winter	Skagerrak-Trondheimsfjord
<i>D. acuta</i> (DSP)	Fall-winter	In <i>C. furca</i> bloom, Skagerrak
<i>D. norvegica</i> (DSP)	Fall-winter	In <i>C. furca</i> bloom, Skagerrak
<i>D. rotundata</i> (DSP)	Summer	Mid-Norway up to N Norway (69°N)
<i>D. spp.</i> (DSP)	May-Oct.	Skagerrak - Stadt
<i>Prorocentrum minimum</i> (VSP)	Summer-fall	Outer Oslofjord
DINOFLAGELLATES ^bAcyloxyfucoxanthins and Chl <i>c</i>₃ group (brown sea)		
<i>Gymnodinium galatheanum</i> (ITOX)	May, Aug-Sept.	Osterfj./Sørfjord (Bergen area), Skagerrak
<i>Gyrodinium aureolum</i> (ITOX)	Aug-Sept.	Skagerrak
HETEROTROPHIC (UNPIGMENTED) DINOFLAGELLATES (red sea)		
<i>Noctiluca scintillans</i> (NH ₄)	Jun-Aug.	German Bight-Skagerrak

^a Bjørnland and Liaaen-Jensen⁴⁸, Johnsen *et al.*¹⁶, Johnsen, unpublished data, ^b Tangen and Bjørnland⁴⁹, Bjørnland and Liaaen-Jensen⁴⁸, Johnsen and Sakshaug¹⁵

3. Monitoring of Harmful Algae Blooms in Norway

3.1 Development of the ALGEINFO service

Since the end of the 1980's, possible causes of harmful blooms of phytoplankton, as well as strategies on mitigating problems associated with harmful algae, have been a focus area for HAB research and management in Norway. Management tools for tackling such problems and minimising losses were developed and include:

1. proper site selection of aquaculture installations,
2. regular monitoring of algae bloom situation,
3. rapid distribution of monitoring information to the industry and public, and
4. risk assessment and operational advice.

Since 1981 a fairly regular monitoring of selected harmful algae has been operative (Dahl, 1989). Simultaneously a monitoring of paralytic shellfish toxins was established (Yndestad and Underdal, 1985). These monitoring and forecasting/information activities have, however, been modified and reorganised several times. For some years in the 1980's the fish farmers organised their own network, "MARINET", for rapid exchange of information including information on HABs, but the service was too costly and complicated especially for the end-users. Then, in the early 1990's, the Norwegian Ministry of Environment funded a program for ocean monitoring and forecasting which included algae (acronym HOV), but this program was terminated after about three years.

The hazard command chain for monitoring of HAB's in Norwegian waters is a public and private funded activity co-ordinated by the Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries. Regular monitoring is done at 27 stations along the coast (Figure 6) with a regular weekly sampling frequency in the period from March to October. The information is made available via the ALGEINFO web-system and can be used free-of-charge by the aquaculture industry. This monitoring service is a joint effort by more than seven Norwegian institutions and is partly financed by the Norwegian State Food Control Authority (SNT), Directorate of Fisheries and the other participants. The main objective of the monitoring program is to provide an early warning of algae blooms that may be a threat to caged fish or cause toxicity in shellfish. Notably, there has been pressure from the aquaculture industry on the Ministry of Fisheries to provide increased governmental support for HAB monitoring activities.

Figure 6. Location of the 27 stations of regular HAB monitoring (Courtesy of E. Dahl, IMR).

Currently the service is mainly based on the use of *in situ* near shore observations from the participating institutions, as well as from information and measurements reported from the numerous aquaculture sites and others located along the Norwegian coast.

The Directorate of Fisheries has implemented a contingency plan for situations of harmful or toxic algae bloom events ("*Varslingsplan for Fiskeridirektoratet ved krisehåndtering in kystsonen - Beredskapsplan 2000*" - "*Contingency plan for the Directorate of Fisheries for emergency situations in the coastal zone - 2000*". This contingency plan implies increased monitoring observations at the regular observation network, re-allocation of research vessel and other ship operations, visual airborne observations, increased ocean modelling and prediction efforts, official decision support and command lines to initiate particular precautions to limit damage effects, mechanisms to communicate information to fisheries, industries and export trade involved etc., as well as press and public awareness etc.. The use of satellite Earth observation data has since 1999 been included in the higher level emergency monitoring resources that can be made available. However, institutional initiatives from the Nansen Center have introduced the use of satellite based sea surface temperature during some earlier major bloom events and during the 1998 *Chatonella* sp. bloom in Danish waters ocean colour was used on an ad-hoc research basis.

3.2 ALGEINFO - How it helps?

Information on the distribution of algae along the Norwegian coast is provided (presently in Norwegian only) via the Internet at the regularly updated (weekly from March to October and less frequently in typically non-HAB winter periods) ALGEINFO web-site with the address, <http://algeinfo.imr.no>. The information at ALGEINFO consists of a station map (Figure 7) indicating the situation of HAB species along the coast and a short text for closer description of the situation in four major regions along the coast of Norway. There are links to useful additional information such as description of various species and their effects. If acute HAB situations should occur more frequent updating is initiated as well as direct contact to management authorities and aquaculture industry in threatened areas.

Attempts have been made to also indicate the potential for development of large harmful blooms based on "extreme" environmental or meteorological conditions, such as high levels of nutrients (nitrate, nitrite), unusual nutrient ratios (N:P) or heavy precipitation (Dahl *et al.*, 1987). In retrospect, this has often failed primarily due to the uncertainties associated with predicting HAB development based on such parameters. *Because of this, at present a more reliable method of early warning of harmful algae blooms may be their early detection by EO systems, and rapid distribution of this information is being investigated.* Combined with ground truth verification and a forecast of further HAB development, such an integrated approach could be a powerful tool. It is noted that one-week advance warning is generally considered sufficient for threatened aquaculture installations to implement mitigation activities prior to an HAB situation. However, any progress in the early warning process and/or forecasting may contribute in reducing the economical loss undergone by the aquaculture industry.

The information in ALGEINFO also helps to provide advice on the risk of mussel toxicity, and a link is provided to the address, <http://www.snt.no/nytt/blaskjell/>. Information on this web-site is also available on a "mussel-phone" or on text-TV (Norwegian Broadcasting). The basis for the advice is primarily data on the occurrence of potentially toxic phytoplankton. Established levels of warning for selected toxic algae (e.g. Andersen, 1996) provide criteria for recommendations. If the levels are exceeded, the public is recommended not to consume wild mussels, and mussel producers are made aware of the fact that their stock of mussels may accumulate algal toxins.

When HABs have occurred in Norwegian waters, efforts have often been made to map the bloom, including its propagation and transport with surface currents. This has most often involved field observations with research vessels, which provided the necessary large-scale observations. In some cases also aircraft and satellite images have been used for mapping of blooms (Dundas *et al.*, 1989; Pettersson *et al.*, 1993; Horstmann *et al.*, 1998). Propagation and transport of blooms have in some cases been recorded by continuous measurements of water movements by anchored buoys (Johnsen *et al.*, 1997) or predicted using models (Durand *et al.*, 1999b).

Havforskningsinstituttet Fiskeridirktoratet Oceanor NIVA

SISTE ALGEINFO
TIDLIGERE ALGEINFO
ALGE DATABASE
MER INFORMASJON
ANDRE SIDER

Dato: 25.11.1999 - Neste algeinfo 09.12.1999

Algeinfo er en ukentlig informasjon som utgis av Havforskningsinstituttet i samarbeide med Oceanor, Fiskeridirktoratet og NIVA. Ønsker du informasjon om hvorvidt blåskjell er spiselige eller ikke anbefales [SNT](#) sin webside.

Fra november til mars er algeovervåkingen redusert til bare noen få stasjoner. I denne perioden oppdateres algeinfoen hver 14.dag.

Generell tekst:
Det er lite alger i hele landet bortsett i fra Sognefjorden og Indre Oslofjord, der det fortsatt er blomstringskonsentrasjoner av kiselalgen *Pseudo-nitzschia*.

Området Finnmark-Vikna (1.2)
Det er god sikt og lite alger i hele området.

Området Vikna-Stad (2.3)
Algemengdene er små og situasjonen nærmer seg vinterminimum, men fortsatt er mange håvtrekk artsrike. Dinoflagellaten *Gymnodinium chlorophorum* som tidligere i høst hadde en oppblomstring i Skagerrak-området, finnes i en del prøver fra Nordmøre til Fosen

Området Stad-Flekkefjord (3.4)
I Lysefjorden dominerer kiselalgene *Chaetoceros compressus* og *Chaetoceros curvisetus*, men konsentrasjonene er forholdsvis små. *Pseudo-nitzschia* blomstrer fortsatt i Sognefjorden.

Området Flekkefjord-Hvaler (4.5)
Pseudo-nitzschia pseudodelicatissima fortsetter den langvarige oppblomstringen i Indre Oslofjord med konsentrasjoner opp til 1.7 mill/L siste uke. I Aust-Agder og i Hvaler-området påvises diarégift i skjell, men konsentrasjonen av *Dinophysis* har avtatt begge steder. I Hvaler-området er det små algebestander, men håvtrekket er variert med *Proboscia alata*, *Dinophysis* sp., *Dictyocha speculum*, *Ceratium* og *Gymnodinium chlorophorum* som vanlige arter. I Aust-Agder (Flødevigen) dominerer *Skeletonema costatum* (90 000 c/L) og det registreres fortsatt små mengder *Gymnodinium chlorophorum*.

25. november 1999

TEGNFORKLARING

- Store algeforekomster
- Moderate algeforekomster
- Små algeforekomster
- † Mye alger, skadelig for fisk
- A *Alexandrium* sp. Alger som kan forårsake PSP (lammelse)
- D *Dinophysis* sp. Alger som kan forårsake DSP (diaré)

Kart

Utviklet av Tor Birkeland og Øyvstein Kristoffer Paulsen ved Forskningsstasjonen Flødevigen

Figure 7. The main ALGEINFO web page (<http://algeinfo.imr.no>) for November 25, 1999 (in Norwegian only). The information content is provided jointly by the Institute of Marine Research (IMR), Directorate of Fisheries, Oceanor AS and NIVA. IMR Flødevigen is responsible for the weekly publishing.

3.3 Role of numerical modelling in an algae bloom monitoring system

The use of coupled 3-dimensional biogeochemical and physical models in algae bloom monitoring systems is still at a research stage, and routinely use of such models are not implemented in the regular efforts. However, during HAB alert events the use of research models in combination with regular ocean forecasting models of the meteorological service have been used in the prediction efforts of the HAB development.

Since the algae can be considered as a “passive tracer”, a good advection physical model will provide useful short-term transport predictions. Most biogeochemical models include only a few functional groups of algae and the model developed and used by IMR, the NORWegian Ecological Model system (NORWECOM) (Aksnes *et al.*, 1995; Skogen *et al.*, 1995; Skogen and Sjøiland, 1998), includes two functional groups, diatoms and flagellates. Most harmful algae species belong to the flagellate group and thus the modelled flagellate concentrations may be used as a proxy for toxic algae during such events. However, due to insufficient knowledge of what triggers bloom developments, NORWECOM (as is the case with most other numerical models of this kind) is not able to predict the occurrence of a bloom of a specific species, and thus the interpretation of the model results is strongly dependent on other observations, which can be used to initiate the occurrence and extent of the bloom in the model system. This was the case in May 1998 during the *Chattonella* bloom in the North Sea and Skagerrak, during which time NORWECOM was run in real time and was used as one of several tools, including also satellite EO data, in monitoring of the bloom. The model results were very useful in combination with *in situ* observations and satellite data of the bloom extension. Importantly, the model was able to forecast bloom development including the growth and movement of this large harmful algae bloom in the threatened region 48 hours into the future.

4. The Users Requirements to Harmful Algae Bloom Information

The core users of the EO based information within the Norwegian algae bloom monitoring service are the service providers and decision-makers. These users include the Directorate of Fisheries (FD), the Institute of Marine Research (IMR) and the other institutions responsible for the information made available at the ALGEINFO web-site. IMR is responsible for making an ecological assessment of HAB situations and may provide recommendations for operational responses to the bloom. However, the FD is the body, which is responsible for making actual decisions on operational responses to such HAB emergency situations and contacting the mass media. The users of this aggregated information for taking decisions for actions are the same authorities and institutions as well as the aquaculture industry and its affiliated organisations, such as the Fisheries Export Council etc..

The scope to the DeciDe-HAB demonstration project does not prioritise an extensive direct end-user survey of the aquaculture industry and its affiliated organisations. The prime aim of the demonstration phase is to identify and demonstrate the role and use of introducing EO data in the harmful algae bloom (HAB) information services mainly provided through ALGEINFO. The analysis of the users requirements to EO based information is in this respect obtained from the main organisations responsible for public HAB monitoring activities in Norway - FD and IMR. The project has also surveyed the information needs from one industrial end-user - AquaFarms Ltd..

The knowledge about EO data and its potential applications are in general limited within the current command chain for monitoring of HAB. However through earlier demonstrations of applications of EO information sources, in particular ocean colour and sea surface temperature data, the willingness and ability to evaluate use of this type of information is most mature within the existing public command chain for monitoring of HAB. In view of this the requirements to EO information are limited and the process of identification of users requirements is regarded as interactively in the process of defining the optimal use of EO information sources within the command chain for monitoring of HAB.

The international regulations (through e.g. FAO ESA- Agricultural and Economic Development Analysis Division and EC Directive 91/492) impose monitoring regulations for toxicity in relation to all kinds of shellfish harvesting. However, similar international regulations are not imposed on fish aquaculture activities since the risk of producing fish, that would be harmful or toxic for consumption due to HAB, is generally low. Based on this the current political priorities in Norway are to develop a network for HAB monitoring to meet the requirements of the growing shellfish industry. The accuracy in identification of this type of algae species and their possible toxic effects is beyond the capabilities of current EO sensor systems and requires analysis of water samples in the vicinity of each shellfish site (Aune et al., 1996).

Within the organisations of the current command chain and activities for HAB monitoring for the aquaculture industry in Norwegian waters the project has identified **four** major fields in which EO data can improve the HAB information provided and the decisions for actions based thereon - i.e.;

- **regular monitoring and early identification** of algae blooms within area for the current Norwegian monitoring as well as extension to surrounding "down stream" waters,
- improvement and optimization of the *in situ* **sampling strategy** under regular and emergency situations,
- **EO data assimilation** for improved model prediction and forecasting of HAB situations, and

- **multi-annual statistics** on the occurrence, extent, life time, etc. of blooms in the Norwegian and adjacent waters in order to improve the scientific understanding of the causes of these blooms.

Access to and knowledge of EO data applications are a limiting factors for non-expert use of satellite data, in this respect the project will be of importance through improvement and facilitation of access to and dissemination of EO based information through a web-site.

4.1 Regular monitoring, early identification and in situ sampling

The ALGEINFO monitoring program is based on sampling and analysis of water samples obtained at fixed locations and times during the regular monitoring mode of operations. During the algae growth season (from March to October) the regular sampling frequency are weekly with sampling every Monday, however at a few locations the sampling is up to three times per week. Most sampling locations are near-shore - in the vicinity of research station locations, local health authority laboratories or at selected industrial aquaculture sites. In addition the FD operates a high speed (35-40 knots) coastal patrol vessel - M/S "Munin", which do regular weekly sampling at six fixed coastal and off-shore locations during the most critical potential HAB periods. The vessel can operate up to 40-50 nautical miles off-shore. The priorities for use of this vessel are however in "competition" with other patrol activities and hence a more optimal use of these resources is essential for the involved institutions. In this respect EO data can provide essential information for the prioritisation of the available or allocations of additional resources in the monitoring efforts.

The water samples are routinely sampled in the surface (0-1 meter) and at the depths of chlorophyll maximum (identified using a profiling fluorometer). The algae specie composition is analysed in the laboratory and cell counts are performed. The regular analysis does not include estimation of chlorophyll concentration (Chl-a), hence a direct comparison between the satellite EO observations and the regularly monitored parameters are not currently possible. Additional net haul are performed from open water locations at 10 to 0 meters depth in order to analyse the algae specie composition.

The following key information requirements are of major concern for the HAB authorities and the aquaculture industry being influenced by HAB's:

- early warning on potential bloom development; with two-three to 11 days notification various mitigation actions can be initiated in order to save values,
- identification and geopositioning of near surface and deeper water layer (usually during the autumn bloom period) algae blooms,
- identification and geopositioning of ocean fronts and boundaries of water masses of different origin,
- localisation of thermal structures and fronts and
- advection and movement of water masses.

For the public HAB monitoring and advice command chain in Norway, the EO-based information is mainly needed in order to improve the early detection of possible algae blooms and then planning of *in situ* observations to confirm possible HAB situations. The current regular field observations is foreseen optimised through tailoring of *in situ* data sampling strategies to cover gradient areas observed in the EO-based chlorophyll concentrations, homogeneous water masses of common origin, thermal front zones and identify advection of water masses in to other areas. The current sampling strategy is based on regional experiences, partly synoptic meteorological forecasts, however direct information on the ocean structures will be new and very useful information. The priorities for use of the coastal patrol vessel, in competitions with other surveillance tasks, will also

be better justified through this type of synoptic ocean information. Since field observations are required to identify eventual HAB species, the absolute accuracy of the EO based chlorophyll estimates is not regarded as very critical. The major application lies within the indications of changes, which then should be used to initiate other actions.

The individual aquaculture site owner (usually larger companies owning several sites) makes their own final decisions on the actual mitigation actions in relation to eventual HAB warning situations of potential threat to their own site locations. The financial impact of wrong mitigation decisions is very significant, hence a high level of precision in the forecasted information is essential! In this respect regional bloom information must be coupled with local knowledge of current patterns, changes in the local weather conditions etc. in order to assess the possible impact of developing bloom situation. This type of local modelling and knowledge is beyond the scope of the public ALGEINFO service to provide, however marine consultant companies are involved in such advisory services for individual aquaculture site owners.

The future tendency is that the aquaculture industry itself is interested in extending its own knowledge basis in order to optimise its profitable activities. The perspective for expansion is that aquaculture and fisheries will become major national sectors of income for Norway in the future. In this respect the industry itself should develop/implement a contingency plan and monitoring activities in order to be better prepared for HAB situations. Currently the public monitoring activities are in this respect a mature user, best prepared to define and evaluate the benefit of using EO based information sources.

4.2 Emergency situation – model forecasting

Regular operational forecasting of the algae bloom situation is not a part of the current ALGEINFO activities. The reason is mainly that the knowledge basis for the initiation of blooms in the models still requires auxiliary information from external sources. Once the initial model conditions and the bloom is identified, the current research models are able to predict the development of an identified bloom, at an acceptable level of precision. The current bio-chemical model tool (NORWECOM - Norwegian Ecological Model System) in use at IMR is based on a physical forcing by the operational ocean circulation model run by the Norwegian Meteorological Institute. The physical ocean circulation model is updated 2-3 times per 24 hours and provides 48 hours forecasts of the ocean currents at a 4 km resolution for the North Sea and Skagerrak region.

EO-derived information products for initiation of a bloom situation in the model as well as for forcing and updating of the model are required. Such information includes sea surface temperature for physical forcing and chlorophyll-a concentration, down-welling irradiance at the sea surface, and estimate of the diffuse attenuation in the water column for ecosystem forcing. The data should be provided in a form directly usable by the model, including grid resolution and projection etc..

For both regular and emergency monitoring situations, FD and IMR require EO data information updates every day or at least images 3-4 times per week. In order to efficiently utilise the information, external expert evaluation and interpretations are required by both institutions.

4.3 Multi-annual statistics

The public and commercial concern on HAB has increased over the last decades. This may be due to the more visible effects on the aquaculture industry as well as an actual change in the annual algae bloom cycle. In this respect the authorities (FD and IMR) need information in the changes of species compositions, dominant species and the actual algae biomass from year to year. Such average values should be acquired at typically weekly intervals, in order to also resolve eventual

variability in the inter-annual timing of the bloom development. Such changes in the annual cycles may have significant negative effects on the recruitment of fish and other marine organisms.

Long-term monitoring of the phytoplankton situation may also be an indicator of local and regional changes in the eutrophication of the North Sea region. Several actions has been initiated in order to reduce the supply of nutrients to the North Sea, and a long term monitoring of the algae bloom pattern and the turbidity of the coastal waters, may in this respect be useful for evaluation of the effects of actions.

These type of longer-term trend change information is of scientific and management interest but in the perspective of the command chain for HAB monitoring, regarded as out of scope for the DeciDe-HAB project activities.

5. Conclusions

The current importance and expected expansion of the aquaculture industry is significant for the Norwegian economy and the employment in coastal areas of Norway. The development of the industry over the last decades placed Norway as the world largest export nation for aquaculture fish species, exporting in 1998, around 390.000 tons of farmed fish (mainly salmon).

The aquaculture industry has many challenges in order to maintain profitable business. Among the challenges are the treats from natural algae blooms in the sea water surrounding the aquaculture sites, blooms which may be harmful or not to the caged fish and/or shellfish. However, in order to implement efficient mitigation actions an early warning of the actual harmful algae bloom events are essential, preferably with one-week notification is need to implement some efficient mitigation actions.

In this respect a regular national monitoring service, operational during the main bloom season from March to October, has been build up in Norway. This ALGEINFO service is based on a network of on-shore coastal observations and analysis, coastal ship observations, and some other ships of opportunity along the entire coastline of Norway. ALGEINFO publishes weekly its information about the algae bloom situation on a web-site available to the public and specifically to the aquaculture industry. During HAB alert situation the information frequency can be increased and a operational co-ordination centre is established at FD to perform daily analysis of the situation, making decisions for public actions and regulations as well as dissemination of information directly to the aquaculture industry, health authorities, the public and media.

The current monitoring and decision making system for harmful algae bloom (HAB) situations in Norwegian waters are strongly pending on early warning and efficient monitoring and predictions of eventually harmful bloom events. This can only be achieved through an efficient observational system in which and integrated approach using multiple information sources, including *in situ* observations from shore and ship locations. Satellite Earth Observation (EO) data and numerical predictions models for simulations of the bloom evolution are two new aspects of HAB monitoring and forecasting which may be further evaluated in the course of the DeciDe-HAB project activities.

With information updates of between daily and three to four times per week, **four** major fields in which EO data requirements have been identified;

- regular monitoring of algae bloom situation in Norwegian waters and improvement the *in situ* sampling strategy, providing information on;
 - early warning of potential bloom developments;
 - identification of near surface and deeper water layer algae blooms;
 - geo-positioning of ocean fronts (in pigment concentrations and thermal structures) and advection of water masses of different origin.
- EO data assimilation for improved model prediction and forecasting of HAB situations, and
- multi-annual statistics on the occurrence, extent, life time, etc. of blooms in the Norwegian and adjacent waters.

Access to and knowledge of EO data applications is a limiting factor for the non-expert use of satellite data within the field of HAB monitoring. Easy access to aggregated EO base information is essential to the users in order to improve the dissemination and actual use among "non-EO expert" users, in this respect dissemination through a dedicated and updated web-site is an efficient mean of information distribution.

The integration of EO based information products with 3-dimensional coupled physical–bio-geo-chemical numerical forecasting models, such as the NORWECOM, and *in situ* observations from station locations along the coast and vessels will significantly improve the capability to forecast HAB events in Norwegian waters. Such an integrated approach, using several sources of information and prediction tools, is one of the major challenging efforts for development towards an improved forecasting of HAB events, which is essential to improve the mitigation efforts implemented by the aquaculture industry.

It is concluded that the awareness of some of the potential information on algae blooms based on EO data sources are present within the current Norwegian monitoring service ALGEINFO as well as the contingency plan for HAB situations in Norwegian waters. A further demonstration, evaluation and implementation through actual demonstration of EO data from ocean colour sensors is required in order to fully explore and define the role and use of EO data in support of the current activities.

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